

Thermal Decomposition of Magnesium Soaps

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Thermal characteristics of magnesium soaps have been studied on an automatic recording thermobalance at a heating rate of 250°/hr. under an ordinary air atmosphere. I. R. spectra and chemical analysis have revealed that the soap molecule is free from water of crystallization. The thermogravimetric analysis has suggested the probable mechanism of decomposition of magnesium soaps.

TRANSITION temperature and approximate heat of transition of several metal palmitates and stearates have been determined¹ from D.T.A. and are found² to have a very restricted correlation in thermal behaviour of alkaline earth and transition metal soaps when these are heated below their decomposition temperature. Barium and calcium soaps when heated are reported³⁻⁶ to give corresponding ketone. Easterfield and Taylor⁷ have shown the presence of an unsaturated ketone in the distilled product of barium salts of oleic acid in an atmosphere of hydrogen. Marwedel⁸ has pointed out that the alkaline earth soaps are non-volatile and give oxides and carbonates on direct ashing. Lorant⁹ has studied the TGA curves of several metallic soaps.

In view of the great importance of magnesium soaps in industry and technology especially as water repelling agents¹⁰, catalysts¹¹, stabilizers and lubricants¹², the thermal characteristics of these soaps have been thoroughly investigated.

Experimental

Preparation of the soaps :

The chemicals have been purified and the soaps prepared by the methods described in a previous communication^{1,3}.

Apparatus and procedure :

The soaps were analysed by standard methods and I.R. spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrometer model 337 using KBr pellet technique.

TGA was carried out using Stanton automatic recording thermo balance (U.K.) at a heating rate of 250°/hr. under an ordinary air atmosphere. The reproducibility of the measurements was examined by repeating them several times.

Results and Discussion

Several magnesium soaps i.e. valerate, caproate, caprylate, caprate and laurate have been analysed and from the microanalysis it is concluded that the soap molecule is free from water of crystallization.

Infra red spectra of magnesium soaps are recorded and tentative assignments of some important vibrations have been made (Table 1). The disappearance of hydroxyl group peak at 3050 cm⁻¹ and the down field appearance of carbonyl functionality at 1600 cm⁻¹ from 1710 cm⁻¹ in its corresponding acid¹⁴ indicates the formation of magnesium soaps. This is further confirmed by the presence of one asymmetrical stretching band near 1600 cm⁻¹ and a weaker symmetrical stretching

TABLE 1—SOME OF CHARACTERISTIC ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) IN MAGNESIUM SOAPS

Valerate	Caproate	Caprylate	Caprate	Laurate	Tentative assignments
2960 (s)	2960 (s)	2870 (s)	2880 (s)	2840 (s)	C-H Stretching vibrations.
1600 (s)	1610 (s)	1580 (s)	1600 (s)	1580 (s)	C=O Stretching vibrations.
1450 (m)	1440 (m)	1450 (m)	1450 (m)	1450 (m)	-CH ₂ Stretching vibrations.
1400 (m)	1410 (m)	1400 (m)	1420 (m)	1400 (m)	Carboxylate anion stretching.

S = strong, m = medium.

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band near 1400 cm^{-1} for carboxylate anion. The presence of water of crystallisation is not indicated in the I.R. spectra of soap because there is no peak in between $3590\text{--}3650\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE 2

Name of the magnesium soap	% yield of MgO	
	Calc.	Found
Valerate	17.78	18.20
Caproate	15.83	16.00
Caprylate	12.99	13.00
Caprate	10.98	10.75
Laurate	9.55	9.50

Fig. 1.

The thermal decomposition of magnesium soap has been studied as a function of temperature. It is observed (Fig. 1) that soap decomposes insignificantly upto 200° , slowly between $200\text{--}300^\circ$, then very rapidly upto 540° and finally shows no change with further increase in temperature. It is suggested that the decomposition occurs with the evolution of corresponding ketone⁶, followed by evolution of carbon dioxide by the decomposition of magnesium carbonate. It may be pointed out that the final weights of soap residue are almost equal to theoretically calculated weight residues from the molecular formula of the soap (Table 2). Therefore, the decomposition of magnesium soap may be represented as :

Soap Ketone

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